

Proceeding on : Parallelisation of Critical Code Passages in PHOENIX/3D

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Abstract

Highly resolved state-of-the-art 3D atmosphere simulations will remain computationally extremely expensive for years to come. In addition to the need for more computing power, rethinking coding practices is necessary. We take a dual approach here, by introducing especially adapted, parallel numerical methods and correspondingly parallelising time critical code passages. In the following, we present our work on PHOENIX/3D.

While parallelisation is generally worthwhile, it requires revision of time-consuming subroutines with respect to separability of localised data and variables in order to determine the optimal approach. Of course, the same applies to the code structure. The importance of this ongoing work can be showcased by recently derived benchmark results, which were generated utilising MPI and OpenMP. Furthermore, the need for a careful and thorough choice of an adequate, machine dependent setup is discussed.

1 Introduction

Exploring and exploiting the advantages of different parallel computing paradigms is vital in search for the most optimal treatment of the diverse problems faced in 3D atmosphere simulations. Therefore we implemented a MPI (Gabriel *et al.*, 2004) based domain decomposition method combined with OpenMP (OpenMP Architecture Review Board, 2013) parallelisation of certain subroutines and code passages.

This paper elaborates on the results shown in the poster ‘Parallelisation of Critical Code Passages in PHOENIX/3D’ at ‘The 19th Cambridge Workshop on Cool Stars, Stellar Systems, and the Sun’. In addition a pseudocode - for better understanding of the described parallelisation efforts - is presented.

2 MPI domain decomposition

When talking about optimisation and parallelisation, it is necessary to understand the underlying program structure. The pseudocode in listing 1 on page 3 shows a simplified version of the basic structure of PHOENIX/3D. The structure of our solution for the radiative transfer problem shows a high degree of possibly independent procedures.

The most important quantities - for parallelisation and a given 3D model structure - are the number of cells holding physical information (n_{voxel} , each cell is call voxel), the number of wavelength-points (n_{wl}) to be considered and the resulting size of information to be stored in memory. Another set of crucial information is the structure and size of the computing facility used for the calculations.

It is necessary to make sure that the model does not surpass the available RAM. Distribution of information is key in this regard, which has been accomplished by a carefully implemented MPI-based domain decomposition. A number

of MPI-processes (procs_per_wl) will be assigned to individual wavelength-clusters, each calculating vital quantities only for a subset of wavelength-points (n_{wlc}).

Within these wavelength-clusters a domain decomposition will be arranged, distributing the data of all voxels across the members of the wavelength-cluster. Each member holds and calculates data only for a fraction $1/\text{procs_per_wl}$ of the total number of voxels n_{voxel} . Communication between the clusters takes place whenever necessary.

The implementation of MPI-based domain decomposition had a massive impact on the performance of the program and is well established by now. Highly resolved 3D atmospheres have shown a excellent scaling behaviour regarding the number of processing units.

Table 1: Benchmark domain decomposition strong scaling

n(MPI)	Cluster size	n(cluster)	Line opacity	3DRT	Total
2048	512	4	96.7%	79.3%	81.9%
2048	256	8	99.1%	97.9%	98.0%
1024	512	2	97.6%	78.4%	81.7%
1024	256	4	100.9%	98.7%	98.9%
1024	128	8	102.2%	110.4%	108.6%
512	512	1	97.8%	79.2%	82.4%
512	256	2	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 1 shows the results of “a small test case for a M dwarf model with 1000 wavelength points in a 3D spherical coordinate system with $n_r = 129$, $n_{\Theta c} = 65$ and $n_{\Phi c} = 129$ points for a total of about 1M voxels and 642 solid angle points” run “with different configurations of the domain decomposition and different total numbers of processes” (Hauschildt & Baron, 2010, Hauschildt *et. al.*).

The total number of MPI processes used $n(MPI)$ is split into $n(\text{cluster})$ domain decomposed clusters. Hence each cluster works with cluster size processes. The values in the

columns *line opacity*, *3DRT* and *total* expresses the parallel efficiency. While the value for *line opacity* and *3DRT* display only the scaling in regards to there respective routines (including communication overhead), the *total* value gives the information about the total computation time for the 3D spectrum, except for the EOS solution and line selection procedures.

3 SMP implementation

While this domain decomposition has proven very potent, memory requirements can limit the number of usable processing units per node. Considering a HLRN-III (HLRN, 2016, Norddeutscher Verbund für Hoch- und Höchstleistungsrechnen) like machine-setup - with 64 GB RAM per computing node with two 12 core CPU sockets - a symmetric distribution of memory leaves each processing unit with 2.6 GB. NLTE radiative transfer problems in 3D can easily exceed the given memory-size per processing unit. This can be counteracted by reducing the number of MPI-processes per node - at the cost of the computing power of these unused cores. To prevent processing units from being forced to idle due to RAM limitations, we are implementing SMP structures with OpenMP to eligible routines or sections. The Fork-Join model of parallel execution allows a simple usage of shared memory for a number of physically connected processing units. Each member of a thread team has full access to their shared memory space, which is held only by this team's master thread. In addition each member holds their own private memory space for auxiliary quantities.

4 Benchmark results: LTE-Line routines

Recently performed benchmark results for some of the LTE-Line routines are shown in figure 1. These routines calculate the LTE absorption coefficients of atomic and molecular lines, differentiated into Gauss- and Voigt-line profiles. The benchmark results were produced on HLRN-III XC30/40 with Intel v16 FORTRAN compiler for a large 3D model.

Figure 1: Relative timings (wallclock time over serial reference time) for LTE-Line routines.

All routines show a noticeable performance increase using two and four threads. It is interesting to note that the run with four threads here was executed with hyperthreading on “only” two physical cores. The hyperthreading causes a hiding of memory latency overhead, decreasing the wallclock time significantly. We expect this behaviour to differ to some extent on other machines.

The execution of OpenMP constructs usually produces some overhead, which in return increases the time needed to perform the same task compared to the serial version. Another interesting result is reflected in the speed increase for the *atomic_voigt* routine with one thread. While all other routines suffer from the described overhead effect, the *atomic_voigt* routine is sped up instead. The wallclock and relative times for each routine summed over 500 different wavelength points are displayed in the respective figures, starting at 5500Å. The label 0 for the number of SMP-threads in the figures refers to the serial reference value.

5 Benchmark results: NLTE opacities

Figure 2: Relative timings (wallclock time over serial reference time) for the NLTE-opacities routine.

Another set of benchmarks has been acquired for the routine *nlte_opacities*. It calculates the opacities for considered NLTE-species.

The plot in figure 2 illustrates the benchmark results for the routine *nlte_opacities*, summing up the wallclock-time for 500 different wavelength points. The serial reference value is again referred to by the label 0 in the number of SMP-threads. The benchmark results were produced on a 6-Core Intel Xeon E5 with Mac-OS and Intel v16 FORTRAN compiler, running with two MPI processes.

Again we can see the expected performance loss of running OpenMP with only one thread. A distinct reduction of computation time for all other numbers of threads can be monitored. The results for four and six threads were produced using hyperthreading.

6 Conclusions

We conclude that it is worthwhile to keep on extending the usage of different parallel computing paradigms, espe-

cially in the face of MPI-3.0 and the recent development for vectorisation units on processors. We find an increase in efficiency in all mentioned routines, speeding up the program run considerably.

References

- Gabriel, E., Fagg, G. E., Bosilca, G., Angskun, T., Dongarra, J. J., *et al.* 2004, In *Proceedings, 11th European PVM/MPI Users' Group Meeting*, pp. 97–104 (Budapest, Hungary).
 Hauschildt, P. H. & Baron, E. 2010, *A&A*, 509, A36.
 HLRN 2016, *Norddeutscher Verbund für Hoch- und Höchstleistungsrechnen*. <https://www.hlrn.de/home/view/Service>.
 OpenMP Architecture Review Board 2013, *OpenMP OpenMP Application Program Interface Version 4.0*.

Listing 1: PHOENIX-Pseudocode

```

Parameters :
mpirun :
    n = total number of MPI processing units
    N = number of MPI processing units per node
    d = number of SMP-threads
    j = hyperthreading off(=1)/on (=2)
phoenix:
    nvoxel = number of voxels in total (e.g from structure)
    proces_per_wl = DDS (choose this)
    nwl = number of wavelength points in total

    nwlc = n/DDS = number of wavelength clusters

```

```

! Initialise MPI structure
! and communication.
! Sets e.g wl_cluster_id for each processing unit

init_mpi()

! Split tasks:
! Each wavelength cluster
! only calculates a set of
! wavelength points < nwl

do i=0, nwl-1, nwlc :

    phx_wl_cluster_tasks(wl=i+w1_cluster_id)(nvoxel)

    ||==>
    ! Split tasks:
    ! Each member of the wavelength
    ! cluster calculates and holds data
    ! only for a fraction of 1/DDS of all voxels,
    ! communicating when ever necessary

    do j=0, DDS-1, 1 :

        phx_wl_cluster_tasks(wl=i+w1_cluster_id)(j*DDS : (j+1)*DDS-1)

        ||==>
        ! Split tasks:
        ! SMP supported routines/sections
        ! will fork and join thread-teams

```
